

ABOUT THE TRANSLATION OF PROVERBS AND SAYINGS

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ABSTRACT

Proverbs are very broad in content. This feature allows large semantic shifts to the article itself, so that a single article can be used in different contexts in different contexts. That fact must be taken into account. Articles clarified between English and Uzbek folk proverbs, as well as proverbs of other nations with their features of glorifying and exemplifying universal qualities, can be created independently as a result of the general progress in the life of each nation, on the one hand, and through the lives of other peoples

The theme of proverbs, and sayings people have always loved and respected their homeland and fought hard against the enemies of the Motherland, its traitors and invaders. That is why in such articles as "The nightingale loves the nature, the man loves the Motherland", "If your motherland is alive, your color will not be straw", "The beggar of the homeland - the beggar of the shroud" finds its concise logical conclusion. Many of the proverbs express true human qualities such as courage, bravery, generosity, justice, honesty, pure love, loyalty, kindness, and high generosity.

Introduction

Phraseologist Kunin, in his Phraseology of Modern English Language, refers to proverbs, parables, and wise sayings and incorporates proverbs and sayings into phraseology and calls them communicative phraseological unit. Russian linguist Babich, in his book Lexicology: A Current Guide, introduces proverbs and aphorisms as two components of spoken phraseology. The proverb is derived from a Latin word, pre-verb and verb-verb. Proverbs are semantically complete and express specific

advice, guidance, or situations that are common truths.

Proverbs, unlike phraseological units, express a complete idea, that is, they come as part of a complete sentence or a complex compound sentence. This is exactly what makes it difficult for us to think of proverbs as phraseological units. The context of folklore do not express a complete idea. They are considered as part of a sentence, both in simple sentences and in complex compound words. For example, East or West, home is best. Now let's look at the use of the phraseological unit: He is as bold as a lion.

Main part

The proverb is derived from the Latin word pro, pre, and verb. Proverbs are semantically complete and provide clear advice and guidance. Proverbs can be full sentences or rhyming short bytes. For example, "Silence is sometimes an answer."

Describing the article, Doctor of Philology, Professor B.Sarimsakov classifies it as follows.

1. A proverb always means a clear complete idea. This opinion is expressed as a firm, concise conclusion. Intellectual clarity is based on a holistic composition that allows for a concise expression of thought.

2. For a proverb, it is characteristic to express a certain idea in a logical conciseness and firm polarity.

3. Proverbs can be used both literally and figuratively. This feature extends the scope of the articles. That is why the proverb is used in parallel in the speech of one or more peoples.

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These qualities do not lose their significance for each person at all times and in all places, and they play a great role in the development of the generation on the basis of high human qualities.

1. Articles between English and Uzbek folk proverbs, as well as proverbs of other nations. Such proverbs, with their features of glorifying and exemplifying universal qualities, can be created independently as a result of the general progress in the life of each nation, on the

one hand, and through the lives of other peoples.

2. Proverbs that reflect the life, worldview, ethical and aesthetic norms, customs of only one people. The national identity of such articles is reflected in the following:

a) directly reflects the socio-political, economic and cultural life, domestic and historical realities of a nation;

(b) in the expression of the diligence, patriotism, love and devotion, courage, devotion, friendship, hospitality and modesty of a people;

(c) a reflection of the toponymy, flora and fauna of a particular population area;

d) in the presence of ethnographic features of a nation;

e) in the language.

Articles in terms of creation:

a) centuries-old social, political, economic experience and observations of the people;

b) they arise on the basis of the spread and popularization of exemplary ideas in the works of this or that poet, writer among the people. Once both articles are in full public use, their author cannot be identified. The anonymous nature of the Creator and its widespread use in oral speech allow proverbs to be collected and studied in the context of folklore.

The artistic form of proverbs serves to reveal their content. This is why essays are so convenient as an independent genre to demonstrate the law of unity of form and content of aesthetics. Proverbs are a genre of philosophical art that is more realistic than other genres of folklore, and it has one of the most important features of art - imagery.

This condition is manifested in the following:

1. The person portrayed in the proverb may seem to us at first as a concrete image, but it reflects all the typical features of a similar person.

The Uzbek article "Diamond cuts diamond" corresponds to the English article "Diamond cuts diamond". These proverbs have the same meaning, but the form of expression is different.

In translating such articles, it is important not only to convey the content, but also to preserve the national identity. Proverbs of this type are usually related to the nature, toponymy, lifestyle, history and spiritual life of each nation.

There is a saying in English, "An oak is not felled with one stroke". In Uzbek, it can be translated as "Islam will gradually", but the English proverb cannot be replaced by the Uzbek proverb related to Islamic culture, because to do so would be to misrepresent a short folk aphorism to flatten national concepts. Leads to perception. Observations show that if there are articles of the third group in the original, that is, proverbs with a specific, national color, it is necessary to translate them in a meaningful, concise, and at the same time figurative way.

Conclusion

Proverbs are short figurative expressions, an example of folk wisdom, with an exemplary meaning and rhythmic-phonetic form. These qualities must be preserved in the translation process. The translation of proverbs, parables, idioms, figurative expressions is one of the most honorable simple events in this field of practice. Each translator has his own way of translating them. Only he can overcome these honorable creative difficulties and achieve success. In addition to knowing the vernacular, he has a strong intuition. The purpose of translating proverbs, parables, idioms, figurative expressions is to find a suitable equivalent in the language of translation, or, if this is not possible, to make sense of it in a concise, wise manner. The translated literature shows that there are many rich and varied experiences in this regard. So as in the proverbs of other nations, the close connection of English and Uzbek proverbs with the life of the people determines both their national identity and universality and finally finds expression in their languages. In this sense, the proverbs of both peoples can be divided into two main parts.

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